

Kinetics and Mechanism of Titanomagnetite Reduction with Charcoal and Soda Ash

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The reduction of Egyptian titanomagnetite with charcoal in presence of soda ash was successfully performed to produce metallic iron and titanium oxide with a recovery of 95%. The reaction rate was found to obey the diffusion of the reactants through the product layer. The activation energies were calculated. A detailed study of X-ray diffraction patterns of the roasting products was performed. A pre-oxidation roasting of the ore before processing was found to improve the recoveries.

THE reducing roast method of titanium iron ores using carbon and soda ash is considered as an efficient process for the production of iron powder and titania at temperatures lower than the slagging temperature¹⁻¹¹. The reduced iron is separated from the residue by magnetic or gravity methods. The remaining titanium rich material can be further processed to produce pigments and certain byproducts.

Solid state reduction roasting of titanomagnetite ore with carbon and soda ash has been studied in the temperature range of 550-1200°⁶⁻¹¹, and the preferentially reduced iron is removed from the roasted products by magnetic separation^{6,7,11} or by dilute sulphuric acid leaching⁶. The amount of sodium carbonate added ranges from 2.0-27%^{4,5,8}. Rapoport and Kozlov⁵ stated that the effectiveness of sodium carbonate was due not only to its action on the carbon but also to its reaction with titanium oxide forming more stable titanium compounds and thus facilitating the reduction of ferrous oxide.

The present investigation was to study the factors affecting reduction of the Egyptian titanomagnetite ore by the reducing roast process using carbon and soda ash to produce iron powder and titanium rich material. Based on the experimental data obtained, the mechanism of the process is also explained.

Experimental

Materials: Egyptian titanomagnetite ore, sample (I) (from the beach sands, Alexandria, Egypt), analysing TiO₂, 17.80; FeO, 18.60; total iron, 56.00; SiO₂, 1.50; Al₂O₃, 1.50% was used. Mineralogy, physicochemical characteristics and X-ray analysis of the ore are reported elsewhere^{1,2}.

The preoxidised titanomagnetite, sample (II), was obtained by heating sample (I) at 900° for 3 hr at atmospheric pressure. X-ray analysis showed that ilmenite mineral has been separated into two phases—rutile and hematite or pseudobrookite^{1,3}.

The samples (I) and (II) were crushed and ground finely to -74 microns before use. Activated charcoal and anhydrous sodium carbonate used were finely powdered and thoroughly dried.

Apparatus and procedure: Finely powdered titanomagnetite sample (I) [or preoxidised titanomagnetite sample (II)] was thoroughly mixed with soda ash and activated charcoal in defined proportions. The mixture was placed into a boat and roasted in a silicon-carbide tube furnace at temp ranging between 600-1100° for various durations under a steady stream of purified nitrogen. At the end of the experiment, the roast product was ground, subjected to chemical analysis and recoveries of metallic iron and titanium oxide were determined.

Results and Discussion

Reduction studies on untreated sample (I):

Effect of carbon and sodium carbonate: To investigate the effect of the addition of carbon and sodium carbonate on the recovery of metallic iron and titanium oxide, two series of experiments were carried out at 900° for 60 min, using titanomagnetite sample (I). The first series consisted of sample (I), sodium carbonate (2.0X) (X=Na₂O : TiO₂ mole ratio) and various proportions of carbon ranging from 0.5-3.5 S (S=C : Fe-oxide mole ratio). The

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second series comprised sample (I), carbon 2.0 S and sodium carbonate in various proportions (0.5-3.5 X).

Fig. 1. Effect of carbon and Na_2CO_3 on the reduction roasting of titanomagnetite ore.

The results, (Fig. 1) reveal that the recovery of metallic iron and titanium oxide markedly increased with the increase in carbon : iron oxide and Na_2O : TiO_2 ratios in the mixture. A maximum recovery of 84% metallic iron and 82% leachable titanium oxide, respectively are achieved within 2.0 S and 2.0 X. Excess of carbon and sodium carbonate has no marked effect on the recoveries.

Effect of temperature and time : Experiments were carried out at various temperatures in the range 600-900° and durations of 60-240 min, using charges containing titanomagnetite sample (I) and the optimum amount of carbon (2.0 S) and sodium carbonate (2.0 X). It is observed (Fig. 2) that recoveries of both metallic iron and titanium oxide increase generally with rise in temperature and duration of roasting. During the first 65 min the reduction of iron oxides proceeds at a considerably high rate, when about 65, 72 and 84% metallic iron and 40, 58 and 82% TiO_2 are recovered at 800, 850 and 900°, respectively. Optimum recoveries of both metallic iron and titanium oxide are obtained after ~120 min at all the temperatures.

Effect of grain size : Five experiments were performed using titanomagnetite sample (I) of grain sizes -124, -88, -74, -43 and -35 microns. The proportion of carbon (2.0 S) and sodium carbonate (2.0 X) in the mixture was maintained at

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature and time on the recovery of metallic iron and TiO_2 from titanomagnetite + Na_2CO_3 + carbon.

the optimum levels and the samples use roasted at 900° for 60 min. Results (Table 1) show that increase in recoveries of both metallic iron and TiO_2 is achieved by reducing the grain size of the ore. Optimum recoveries of 90-92% of both are obtained with grain sizes of -43 and -35 microns. However, grinding to such fineness will be expensive commercially and will also cause semifusion. It is, therefore, preferable to use titanomagnetite of grain size -74 microns which also yields high recovery of both iron and titanium oxide.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF GRAIN SIZE ON REDUCTION ROASTING OF TITANOMAGNETITE SAMPLE (I) IN PRESENCE OF CARBON AND SODA ASH AT 900° FOR 60 MIN

Products %	Grain size, microns				
	-124	-88	-74	-43	-35
Fe, metallic	60.90	80.60	84.00	90.90	91.60
TiO_2	47.80	63.60	82.40	92.30	92.60

Reduction studies on preoxidised sample (II) :

Preoxidised sample (II) of grain size -74 microns was subjected to reduction roasting using carbon (2.0 S) and soda ash (2.0 X) at different tempera-

tures ranging from 600-1100° for 60 min. Percentage recoveries of metallic iron and titanium oxide were determined and compared with those of untreated ore sample (I) (Fig. 3). The results reveal that the recovery of metallic iron and titanium oxide, obtained with the preoxidised sample (II) is higher than that of the untreated one at all the temperatures used. Moreover, the maximum recovery of 93% metallic iron and 87% TiO₂ are obtained on roasting at 900°.

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on the recovery of metallic iron and TiO₂ from titanomagnetite samples. 1 and 2 untreated T.M. ore samples. 3 and 4 Preoxidised T.M. ore samples.

X-ray analysis of products :

X-ray analysis of the products of sample (I), after roasting for 180 min at 700, 800 and 900° were undertaken and Fig. 4 shows the Debyogram of the products, together with the same for standard compounds (ASTM cards). These reveal that the main X-ray diffraction patterns of the products are, in general, similar to those of α -Fe and sodium titanates. Patterns obtained at 700° and 800° show that the main lines correspond to those of α -Fe, Na₂TiO₃ and Na₂Ti₃O₇ together with faint lines of wustite, maghemite and ilmenite. On the other hand, the main lines at 900° correspond to α -Fe, Na₂TiO₃ (Na₂O.TiO₂), Na₂Ti₃O₇ (Na₂O.3TiO₂) and their recrystallised form of Na₈Ti₅O₁₄ (4Na₂O.5TiO₂) (these formulae of sodium titanates are in good agreement with those obtained with synthetic mixtures^{14,15}). The disappearance of wustite and maghemite patterns is worthnoting.

Fig. 4. X-ray Debyograms of roasted products of T.M. sample (I) at various temperatures and ASTM patterns.

Mechanism of reaction :

The mechanism of the reduction of titanomagnetite with carbon in presence of sodium carbonate to metallic iron and titanium oxide (as soluble sodium titanates) can be considered to be a complicated process and hence any mathematical calculations must be formulated in terms of the nature of the interfaces present. The solid-solid and solid-gas interfaces are considered in terms of magnitude of area, geometric form, deficit structure and solid stoichiometry.

We investigated the following kinetic equations to calculate the activation energies of iron oxide/carbon and titanium oxide/sodium oxide systems.

1) Equation for product growth controlled by product nucleation at each active site. It is applicable for reactions which are controlled neither by diffusion of the reactants and the products from the boundary region nor by the catalytic nature of the interfaces¹⁶.

$$-\ln(1-x) = Kt \quad \dots (2)$$

2) Equation for product growth, which is applied for spherical symmetry solid reacting material for phase boundary reactions. It depends only on interface controlled reaction and does not ignore the diffusion processes which are usually the slowest step¹⁷.

$$1-(1-x)^{1/3} = Kt \quad \dots (3)$$

3) Equation for product growth controlled by diffusion of reactants through a product layer¹⁸ starting on the exterior of a spherical particle of radius r_0 .

$$1 - 2x/3 - (1-x)^{3/2} = (k/r_0^2) t = K't \quad \dots (4)$$

4) Equation for product growth controlled by the application of the recommendations of Sharp¹⁹ and Satava²⁰ for three dimensional diffusion reaction. It is convenient in comparing the experimental data to apply the reduced scale²¹ such as $t/t_{0.5}$, where $t_{0.5}$ correspond to time (t) when $\alpha=0.5$ recovery at different temperatures. Thus :

$$[1 - (1-\alpha)^{1/2}]^2 = (k/r_0^2) t = 0.0426 (t/t_{0.5}) \quad \dots (5)$$

where,

x or α = fraction reaction after time (t),

K = rate constant,

k = specific rate constant, and

r = radius of reactant particles.

Applying the above mentioned equations (2, 3 & 4) and using results shown in Fig. 2, the plots of $f(x)$ vs time show that the best fit is obtained using equation (4). The equation describes the reaction kinetics at 600-900° and up to 120 min roasting. Deviation started thereafter, and was noticed more at higher temperatures. Slopes of the plots of $1 - 2x/3 - (1-x)^{3/2}$ vs time (Fig. 5) at different temperatures represent the term k/r_0^2 or K' at that temperature if r_0 is considered to be the same for all the samples.

Fig. 5. Plot of $[1 - 2X/3 - (1-X)^{3/2}]$ against time for the result of Fig. 2. A. for metallic iron, B. for TiO_2 .

From the values of these slopes, an Arrhenius plot of $\log K'$ vs $1/T$ was constructed, and straight lines were obtained (Fig. 6). The apparent activation energies were found to be 36.40, 9.20 and 30.80 K.cal.mole⁻¹ for reduced metallic iron and soluble titanium oxide at different temperatures (Fig. 6; lines 1, 1' and 2). Besides, it is convenient to apply equation (5), using the α values of metallic iron and titanium oxide given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 6. Scale A. $\log k' - 1/T$ (lines 1, 1' and 2) and Scale B. $\log t_{0.5} - 1/T$ (lines 3 to 6).

We, thus, found that in case of the preoxidised sample (II), metallic iron and titanium oxide recoveries are greater than those obtained from untreated sample (I). Also, the activation energies of preoxidised sample (II) are lower than those of the untreated sample (I). The values of activation energies calculated applying equations (4) and (5) at different temperature and duration periods of roasting, confirm diffusion as the rate determining step of the process.

The chemical reactions occurring during the reduction of titanomagnetite by charcoal at temperature up to 800° may be considered as the solid-solid interaction at the contact point between the reactants,

At temperatures > 800°, the increase in reduction recovery would depend upon the diffusion of carbon monoxide through the grains and the gaseous reduction of titanomagnetite structure,

It is worth mentioning that the TiO_2 produced (equations 6 and 7) combines with sodium oxide forming sodium titanates of different composition, which accelerates the reduction rate.

The higher recoveries of metallic iron and titanium oxide in the case of the preoxidised sample (II) may be attributed to some disturbance in the solid solution structure existing in the titanomagnetite ore. It seems that pseudobrookite [as shown in equation (1)] is more susceptible to reduction by carbon than the original minerals of titanomagnetite ore.

The behaviour of titanomagnetite reduction roasting at temperatures $>900^\circ$ (Fig. 3) may be explained on the premise of various intermediate compounds. Such compounds result from the combination of metallic iron and TiO_2 or its reduced forms which slightly decreases the reduction recovery of metallic iron obtained at different period. Presumably, at the high temperatures ($>800^\circ$), sodium and oxygen ions diffuse into the TiO_2 lattice, which results in the formation of the compounds with a low Na content, $(Na_xTi_5O_{14})$ which is observed in X-ray analysis of the roasted products being formed later.

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